

TRYING TIMES

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I hope you are well in these trying times...

Remember during Covid when it was commonplace to get e-mails that started “Dear colleague, I hope you are well in these trying times.” I find myself feeling that we have once again entered trying times.

In the Netherlands, like so many other places, higher education is under fire. We are facing budget cuts that go far beyond “working a little more effectively”; redundancy and reorganizations have been announced for so many of our universities, and today Utrecht joined in with [the announcement that 80-100 full-time equivalents](#) will be cut, which will affect many more people than that as many of these jobs are not full time.

These cuts are being made in support staff, which means the people who work on our education policies, media, ICT infrastructure, and HR, to name just a few. Talented people who set up projects, are the long-term memory of our organization, ensure our contact with society, and do any number of other things that make the university not just function, but into a better place.

In the same period highlights of [our new Utrecht University strategic plan were announced](#), which is a lifeline for me, as it so clearly aligns with my values and activities... working with local and regional partners, a broad take on sustainability, integrating societal engagement into university education- this is all very much what I do and stand for.

But it is hard to envision how this is all going to continue in the face of these budget cuts. Aside from the loss of colleagues and the fact that much work will now be redistributed to others who are already overtaxed, it is disheartening to feel that society does not value universities as a place for independent thought, innovative research, and life-

course altering education. And this is just in our small corner of the world; nationally, Dutch higher education is facing draconian austerity measures, while internationally, well, let's not start about [the state of higher education in the US](#).

I continue to work toward integrating animals into sustainability concepts, and education of future veterinarians to engage with society and the societal questions that matter, and sincerely hope that the pendulum swings back before even more knowledge, capacity and hope are lost. I am generally a glass-half-full person, but the potential return to silos and ivory towers [keeps me up at night](#).